

Fuel cells and battery technology in the age of electric vehicles: Have Europe and North America bet on the wrong horse?

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Introduction

As a major transition to electric vehicles (EVs) appears to be gaining momentum, governments are increasingly recognising battery technology as a field of strategic importance. Particularly in the US, there is growing concern that Asian strengths in battery technology could give Japanese, Korean and Chinese industry an important competitive advantage in hybrid, plug-in hybrid and pure electric vehicles (Brodd, 2005; Grove and Burgelman, 2008; Murphy, 2008). This may have prompted the Obama administration to offer US\$1.5 billion in grants to US manufacturers of advanced batteries. At the same time, automotive industry and government interest in hydrogen and fuel cell vehicles appears to be waning. While demonstration activity continues, many now believe EVs have much stronger chances of achieving commercial success (King, 2007; Romm, 2006).

Methods

What do these trends imply for the firms, industries and countries that have invested heavily in fuel cells while neglecting battery technology? In the present study, we use patent statistics, based on a dataset comprising over 30,000 power source related US patents and complemented by qualitative industry data, to show that the automotive industry, and European industry in general, may have over-invested in fuel cell technology relative to battery technology. In fact, Japan and Korea have increasingly specialised in batteries (Table 1).

In addition, industry specialisation index scores and other data reveal that, compared to other sectors, the automotive industry (including Japanese manufacturers) has tended to invest more on fuel cell technology than batteries. Only the academic sector places more emphasis on fuel cells than the auto industry. Partly as a result of this imbalance in IP, vehicle manufacturers developing hybrids and EVs are forced to work with established consumer electronics manufacturers such as Panasonic and Sanyo, who are the driving forces of innovation in battery technology since the 1980s.

Two major implications may be drawn. On the one hand, strong technological and organisational linkages between the automotive and consumer electronics industries, which share a similar requirement for high energy density electricity storage, could accelerate the development and commercialisation of EVs. These linkages allow vehicle developers to draw on a steady flow of spillovers from the consumer

electronics industry, including technological innovations, skilled workers and engineers, cheap materials, high-volume manufacturing capacity and related know-how (Beaudet, 2010).

On the other hand, the wider trend is clear: if the world transitions to electric vehicles, Asian countries led by Japan stand to benefit the most (Figure 1). Indeed, not only does Japan dominate in terms of patents and specialisation, but its patents are also more cited, on average, than those of most other countries (with the exception of the US, which benefits from the home country bias effect). In Japan, spillovers from local consumer electronics industries are complemented with in-house knowledge of batteries gained through R&D as well hybrid vehicle development and manufacturing. Indeed, while all vehicle manufacturers are dependent on the (Asian) consumer electronics industry for battery technology, Japanese car manufacturers have tended to invest more in battery technology R&D than their European and American peers (supporting data to be included in final paper). Only time will tell if recent efforts to redress the situation in the US and Europe can rebalance the terms of trade in battery technology.

Table 1. Fuel cell & battery patents

Years:	Number of patents				Specialisation index (SI)			
	80-86	87-93	94-00	01-07	80-86	87-93	94-00	01-07
World – Fuel Cells	441	659	1094	3805	1	1	1	1
North America – FC	300	380	624	2217	1.10	1.01	0.97	1.06
Europe – FC	70	75	195	448	0.74	0.60	1.17	0.78
Japan/Korea - FC	66	196	278	1096	0.97	1.36	1.11	1.17
World – Batteries	1966	1938	3699	4372	1	1	1	1
North America –B	1323	1194	2020	1770	1.09	1.08	0.93	0.74
Europe – B	363	301	342	349	0.86	0.82	0.61	0.53
Japan/Korea – B	229	412	1221	2139	0.76	0.97	1.44	1.99
World – All	457148	644627	894295	1162035	-	-	-	-
North America - All	282210	369374	526740	639790	-	-	-	-
Europe - All	97658	121967	136018	176264	-	-	-	-
Japan/Korea - All	70226	141080	205010	285673	-	-	-	-

Figure 1. Positioning of leading countries in battery technology (as of end of 2007)

Source: Computed by Alexandre Beaudet and Science-Metrix using UPSTO data

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